

Studies on Dithiocarbamates: Part XI. Solvolysis of 3-Benzyl-5-Phenylazorhodanine

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Solvolysis of the titled compound was examined under various conditions. Rate coefficients at constant pH (~ 11.0) are strongly dependent on the nature of medium. Observed data could be reconciled by taking a number of solvent parameters, in particular, the pK_a of the solvent was found to be the most important factor. The discrepancy between observed and calculated rates is maximum when the solvent to water ratio is 1 : 3 (mole).

In our previous studies^{1,2} we have covered several aspects of azorhodanine chemistry including base-catalysed decomposition of I in 40% aqueous-methanol². However, the kinetic behaviour reflected certain features which, we feel, require further clarification. For example, the proposed mechanism^{2,3} demanded the formation of a solvent-stabilised anion(II) but the mode of intervention of the solvent could not be delineated. Consequently, solvolytic studies^{4,5} which already encompassed a vast amount of data, are anticipated to provide the necessary information. In this context, we discuss here the influence of solvent on the rate coefficients of decomposition of 3-benzyl-5-phenylazorhodanine (I) at constant pH and temperature.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials: The azorhodanine has been previously described by us¹. AR-grade solvents were fractionated over metallic sodium, the mid-fractions were stored in amber coloured bottles prior to their use, and calibrated by checking the specific gravities against lit. values. The alkali solution ($\sim 1.0M$, NaOH) was prepared in conductivity water. Spectrophotometric measurements were carried out with Hilger UVISPEK spectrophotometer in 1 cm. cells.

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Kinetic Measurements : A stock solution of the azocompound was first prepared in an appropriate solvent. Aliquots of this solution were diluted with a mixture of the same solvent and water containing sufficient alkali so that the final pH was around 11.8 and by suitable adjustments, solvent to water ratio (v/v) was varied over a wide range. After proper mixing the loss of intensity at 480 m μ was measured at regular intervals until the optical density asymptotically approached zero.

In acetone solution, change in colour intensities was complicated by secondary reactions. Although suitable blank corrections were applied, o.d. values were used only as long as these fitted into the first order plots.

At the end of measurements, pH was always ~ 11.0 and the constancy of temperature was better than $\pm 0.2^\circ$. Other details were as previously described^{2,3}.

Solvent Parameters : These were taken from appropriate sources with the following assumptions : pK_a value of acetone is taken from Hine⁶ and the rest from the compilation of Bowden⁷. Dielectric constants are from Weissberger⁸ and in absence of known value of 2-ethoxy ethanol the quoted value refers to that of the methyl ether. Taft σ^* values⁹ for ethylene glycol and its ether were derived by applying an attenuation factor of 0.33 to the σ^* values of lower homologues. Acetone and isopropanol were assumed to have the same σ^* and E_s values. E_s values⁹ for OH-CH₂-CH₂- and Cl-CH₂-CH₂- were assumed to be identical.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Variation of rates with solvent : Earlier studies^{2,3} have shown that under alkaline condition decomposition of the substrate anion(II) is the rate-determining step. Influence of any change in pK_a value ($\sim 8 \cdot 10^{10}$ in 40% aqueous methanol) is discounted under the experimental condition. Hence conclusions drawn on previous observations are still valid. Moreover, as the substrate concentration is sufficiently low ($\sim 1 \times 10^{-4}M$), the anion may be assumed to exist essentially as monomeric because of strong solvent action. From a consideration of decomposition products^{3,11} of II, it appears that the net ionic character of the solution would not be significantly affected during the experimental work.

Pseudo first-order rate coefficients (k_{ob}) under different experimental conditions are noted in Table 1. Inspection of data clearly shows that the rate coefficients are sufficiently sensitive to solvent composition, and at any given point the following decreasing order is observed: methanol > glycol > ethanol > 2-ethoxyethanol > isopropanol > acetone. It is particularly striking that the plots of $\log k_{ob}$ against solvent composition (% v/v) tend to meet

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TABLE I

Pseudo-first order rate coefficients, $10^4 k_{ob}$ in sec.^{-1} , in different solvent-water composition at constant temperature 25° and pH.

Solvent	% Solvent, v/v								
	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90
Glycol	0.685	0.738	0.741	0.760	0.754	0.775	0.839	0.768	0.912
Glycol ether	0.279	0.167	0.123	0.0896	0.0782	0.0704	0.0704	0.0663	0.0663
Methanol	0.945	1.150	1.300	1.370	1.380	1.420	1.460	1.570	1.690
Ethanol	0.463	0.389	0.286	0.230	0.215	0.186	0.178	0.172	—
Iso-propanol	0.298	0.134	—	0.0494	—	0.0288	—	0.0192	0.0124
Acetone	0.162	0.0831	0.0388	0.0172	0.0118	0.0103	0.00926	0.00872	0.00628

at a point with increasing water content in the mixture, whereas rise or fall in rate coefficients is very much dependent on the nature of the solvent. From the observed trend it is thus possible to calculate with reasonable accuracy the hypothetical second order rate coefficients in 100% solvent (k_s) from the extrapolated values ($\log k_{ob}^\circ$) of $\log k_{ob}$ vs. solvent composition (Fig. 1). These results along with some solvent parameters are shown in Table 2.

Fig. 1—Variation of rate constants against solvent composition, experimental points and calculated lines. (MeOH—○; EtOH—▲; i-PrOH—■).

Influence of solvent polarity: For a typical SN_1 reaction, rate coefficients could be related to the ionising power of the medium as expressed by Winstein-Grunwald equation¹², $\log(k/k_0) = my$. But our results provided breaks in all cases. Presumably, ionisation of I is not critical. This is in agreement with our previously proposed mechanism

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TABLE 2

Calculated rate-coefficients and solvent parameters.

Solvent	$\log k_{ob}^0$	$\log k_s$	pK_a	ϵ	σ^*	E_s
Glycol	$\bar{5}.96$	$\bar{6}.71$	16.68	37.0	+0.18	-0.90
Glycol ether	$\bar{6}.82$	$\bar{7}.81$	17.23	16.0	+0.17	-0.77
Methanol	$\bar{4}.25$	$\bar{6}.86$	17.71	32.6	0.00	0.00
Ethanol	$\bar{5}.10$	$\bar{7}.86$	18.33	24.3	-0.10	-0.07
Isopropanol	$\bar{7}.83$	$\bar{8}.72$	19.43	18.3	-0.19	-0.47
Acetone	$\bar{7}.60$	$\bar{8}.47$	20.0	20.7	-0.19	-0.47
Water	$\bar{5}.83$	$\bar{6}.09$	18.23	78.5	+0.49	1.24

($\log k_h$)

where passage of anion (II) to the transition state is believed to be critical. Again, sensitivity of the transition state to solvent composition suggests as if the transition state is somewhat more polar than the reactant. In this respect, there is a formal resemblance, although somewhat tenuous, to separation of charges as in a typical SN_2 reaction. Hence rate coefficients (k_s) should increase with increase in polarity of the solvent⁴. Using dielectric constant (ϵ) of the solvent as a measure of its polarity, no satisfactory trend could be discerned between $\log k_s$ and $1/\epsilon$. But there is qualitative agreement with this concept in three cases only, viz., methanol, ethanol and isopropanol. This behaviour is not surprising as microscopic dielectric constant around the reactant is quite different from its bulk. Analogous conclusions were recently drawn by several groups of workers^{13,14} in their attempts to correlate rate-coefficients against ϵ .

Role of specific interaction: On the basis of the above discussions it is not unreasonable to suspect the presence of specific interactions at the transition state when the transition energy may be significantly altered. In other words, participation of the solvents in the alkaline decomposition of I should be accepted. Consequently, k_{ob} must reflect the composite effect of at least two simultaneously occurring reactions, and the overall reaction may therefore be expressed as :

$$k_{ob} = k_h[H_2O] + k_s[solv] + k_{xy}[XY] \quad (1)$$

where k_h and k_s are the rate coefficients in water and solvent respectively; and the third term includes the sum of all secondary interactions arising through various acid-base equilibria.

13. A. Buckley, N. B. Chapman, M. R. J. Daek, J. Shorter and H. M. Wall, *J. Chem. Soc. (B)*, 1968, 631.

14. M. A. P. Dankleff, R. Curci, J. O. Edwards and H. Y. Pyun, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 3209.

Restricting ourselves to the first two terms in equation (1), the calculated second order rate-coefficients (k_s) should show sensitivity to the protic character of the solvent. This was indeed found to be the case when one uses pK_a values of the solvent, but serious deviations were found for glycol and 2-ethoxyethanol. Acidity of the solvent is thus an important factor, but other factors presumably come into play under specific condition. It is interesting to recall the observation of Chapman and his coworkers¹³ that basicity of alcohol was an important factor in correlating the esterification of benzoic acids by diazodiphenylmethane in various solvents. Similarly, oxidation of thioxane by hydrogen peroxide¹⁴ is better correlated by protic character of the solvent.

Since interaction of the above kind is not solely governed by the acidity of the solvent, it appears that 'bulk' of the solvating molecule may adversely affect its participation at the transition state. This is of course a well known phenomenon and the difference in basicity of the *tertiary*-aliphatic amines is a case in point. Besides, two additional basic centers are involved in glycol and its ethyl ether which might influence the results.

But the third term in equation (1), which has been so far neglected, seems to have some bearing when one scrupulously examines the plots of $\log k_{ob}$ vs solvent composition. Thus the rate-coefficients tend to change rather sharply when the solvent content is appreciably high ($\sim 90\%$, v/v); in particular, the phenomenon becomes conspicuous in isopropanol and acetone. According to Burns and England¹⁵, the hydroxide content (\overline{OH}) in $ROH + \overline{OH} \rightleftharpoons \overline{RO} + H_2O$ equilibria is not only dependent on the type of ROH but there is a great deal of tendency for the anion to remain associated with the cation, especially with high ROH content in the medium. Surely, the phenomenon of ion-pair formation would attain some importance under these conditions and might impair the "electrophilicity" of the solvent system. This is undoubtedly more important in weakly polar medium. Evidently it is hard to establish the magnitude of the contributions arising through such secondary interactions. However, for the sake of simplicity, this kind of interaction may be neglected at least under conditions where the solvent content is around 80% or lower.

Correlation of $\log k_s$ with solvent parameters: Analysis of our solvolysis data clearly demonstrates that the rate-coefficients are simultaneously affected by several parameters, namely, acidity (pK_a), polarity (ϵ) and some other parameter reflecting steric requirement. Since Taft σ^* and E_s values⁹ give a measure of microscopic polarity and steric requirement, these were also included to evaluate our data and the best correlation may be expressed by the following equation (excluding water): $\log k_s = 9.83 - 0.842 (pK_a + 10/\epsilon + \sigma^* - E_s)$, giving $r = 0.985$; $s = 0.029$.

Although some reasonable assumptions were made regarding solvent parameters (*vide* Experimental), the magnitude of correlation coefficient (Fig. 2) confirms that solvation of the anion is indeed subject to some steric requirement, but the effect is small. Transition state may therefore be visualized to resemble more or less the anion stabilised through

hydrogen bonding by the solvent. Presumably, high polarity of the medium is beneficial, but not decisive. This view is also consistent with the sign and magnitude of entropy of activation ($-\Delta S^* \approx 12$ e.u.) observed in 40% aqueous methanol.

Fig. 2—Correlation of second order rate constants against solvent parameters.

The above equation (excluding the interaction term), however, affords only a qualitative agreement between the observed and calculated rates, and appreciable discrepancy could be noted with solvents of high pK_a values (Fig. 1). Evidently, use of stoichiometric

Fig. 3—Difference in observed and calculated rates against mole fraction of the solvents.

concentration in the above equation is inappropriate. While it is difficult to offer any straightforward explanation for this behaviour, we would like to draw attention to a few subtle points which reflect the existence of some kind of intra- and/or intermolecular association in the medium. Thus, it is remarkable to find that the plots of difference between observed and calculated rates against mole fraction of the solvent was found to exhibit a peak as shown in three typical cases (Fig. 3). Further, it is striking that the peak practically appears in the same region ($\sim 1 : 3$ mole ratio) for all the solvents, the height of which increases in the order methanol, ethanol and isopropanol.

For hydroxylic solvents like water and alcohol, clustering¹⁶ of solvent molecules either alone or in combination is a recognised phenomenon. This would undoubtedly reduce the effective monomer concentration causing some error in the calculated rates. Similarly, hydroxide or alkoxide ion is believed⁷ to be associated with three molecules of solvent; the observed ratio is therefore not inconsistent with known intrinsic properties of the hydroxylic solvents¹⁶. Since the deviation is maximum for the solvent of lowest acidity, it seems likely that hydrogen bonding is a major factor in helping the molecules to associate.

TABLE 3

Effect of Ionic strength on rate coefficients.

Soln.	Ionic strength	$10^4 k_{ob}$, sec. ⁻¹
40% Ethanol	~ 0.0	0.230
„	0.1	0.244
„	0.5	0.256
40% Methanol	~ 0.0	1.380
„	0.1	1.400

Finally, five-fold increase in the ionic strength of the medium was found to have only a marginal effect on the rates as shown in Table 3. This is also in agreement with the suggested criterion¹⁷ of a reaction between an ion and a neutral molecule.

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